

The success by chance in criterion-referenced multiple-choice tests

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Abstract

Some time ago, in my Department, some colleagues put me the following question: when we classify the multiple choice tests, is it necessary to introduce a correction factor, having in account that students can get correct answers by chance? If yes, how to proceed? I studied and thought about the subject, and this communication synthesizes the answer that I presented, sometime later, in the Department in what concerns to the criterion-referenced tests.

1. It is fundamental the quality of the items and the number of options

In a good multiple choice question the options are homogeneous and the wrong answers (called “distracters”) are not obviously incorrect. In an ideal situation, the student that doesn't know the answer of a question with n options, and tries to guess it, has the probability $\frac{1}{n}$ of getting right in that item. Well, but a test of multiple choice has N items and as long is N better is the reliability of the test. And we must have in account that the most important objective of a test is the formulation of well founded value claims, based on good referents, in order to make good decisions, having previously in account the purposes of the test. But, those referents differ and the differences will have implications in value claims, as we will see in the following section.

2. The proficiency level in criterion-referenced tests

Three of the important characteristics of a *criterion-referenced test* are the following ones (Valadares and Graça, 1998, pp. 48 a 50):

- The *domain of objectives* to assess is more or less narrow, with several items used to measure the so called level of proficiency of each objective.

- What we intend with the *analysis of the answers* is to describe the proficiency level in each objective.
- The *results* must be expressed in terms of the proficiency level of the test objectives.

The following table exemplifies in what consists the proficiency level:

PROFICIENCY IN WHAT? PROFICIENCY OF WHO?	IN AN ONLY OBJECTIVE	IN A GROUP OF OBJECTIVES
OF ONE STUDENT	He/she gets of a bar graph two of the three asked information	She/he demonstrates proficiency in six of the ten objectives assessed with the test
OF A GROUP OF STUDENTS	90% of the students reach the objective regarding the reading of bar graphs	80% of the students satisfy in the test

Table 1 - The proficiency level (A. Ribeiro and L. Ribeiro, 1989, p. 310)

Some proficiency levels depend on the other ones, as the arrows try to show. For instance, the level of each student's proficiency in each objective determines his/her proficiency level in all objectives assessed with the test. The problem, now, is this: if we built a given number N of questions for the same objective, what is the minimum proficiency level that we should demand to guarantee that the objective was sufficiently reached by a student, having in account that he/she might have gotten right by chance?

Let us suppose that we used two questions to assess a given objective ($N = 2$), each of them with 4 options ($n = 4$). In terms of chance, everything is possible, otherwise nobody got right in the most

several lucky games, and this fact takes us to the field of the probabilities.

What is the probability to get right by chance in anyone of the two questions constructed to assess the same objective? The probability of getting right in the first question is $1/4$. The probability of wandering in the second question is $3/4$. Then, the probability of the united production of these two events, that is, to get right in the first question and to wander in the second one, is the product of the respective probabilities: $1/4 \times 3/4 = 3/16$.

In a similar way, we conclude that the probability of wandering in the first question and to get right in the second one is the product of the respective probabilities: $3/4 \times 1/4 = 3/16$.

Then, as these two events, to get right in any one of the questions and to wander in the other, are independent, the probability of one of them, whichever it is, is just the sum of the probabilities of each of them:

$$3/16 + 3/16 = 6/16 = 0,375 = 37,5 \%$$

In the same way, the probability of getting right, by chance, in 2 questions with 4 options, is:

$$1/4 \times 1/4 = 1/16 = 0,063 = 6,3 \%$$

These probabilities of getting right by chance in all of the questions, or in half of them, for instance, decrease when the number of questions increases, and they decrease also with the number of options. The calculation of the probabilities, allied to the combinatory analysis, allowed us to construct the following tables¹

N° OF QUEST / N° OF RIGHT ANSWERS	2	3	4	5	6	8	10
1	37,5	42,2	42,2	39,6	35,6	26,7	
2	6,3	14,1	21,1	26,4	29,7	31,1	
3		1,6	4,7	8,8	13,2	20,8	
4			0,4	1,5	3,3	8,6	
5				0,1	0,4	2,3	5,8
6					0,0	0,4	

Table 2 - Probabilities (in percentages) of getting right, by chance, in questions with 4 options

¹ For instance: the probability of getting right by chance in the first three of five items with four options, wandering in the other two, is $1/4 \times 1/4 \times 1/4 \times 3/4 \times 3/4 = (1/4)^3 \times (3/4)^2$. As there is 5C_3 different ways of distributing the 3 successes for the 5 items, the probability of getting right by chance in 3 any items is ${}^5C_3 \times (1/4)^3 \times (3/4)^2 = 0,088 = 8,8\%$

N° OF QUEST / N° OF RIGHT ANSWERS	2	3	4	5	6	8	10
1	32,0	38,4	40,9	40,9	39,3		
2	4,0	9,6	15,4	20,5	24,6		
3		0,8	2,6	5,1	8,2		
4			0,2	0,6	1,5	4,6	
5				0,0	0,2		2,6
6					0,0		

Table 3 - Probabilities (in percentages) of getting right, by chance, in questions with 5 options

In these tables, the percentages of getting right by chance in half of the questions have been particularly marked. We see, then, that using 6 questions of 4 options to assess a particular objective, the student has the probability 13,2% of getting right in half of them (3 questions). And if the questions have 5 options, that probability decreases to 8,2%. Nothing impedes that we stipulate the success in 4 of the 6 questions as the proficiency criterion for that objective. Doing this, the probabilities of revealing proficiency in the objective decreases to 3,3% using questions with four options, and 1,5% using questions with five options.

3. Looking for a classification criterion

The question, now, is this: if a student has 4 correct questions, in 6, how many answers had been guessed? Only he knows! Then, we have to adopt a criterion. But what is it?

Let us go to analyze two possible processes of going to the encounter of a classification criterion. Any of them has already been adopted.

1st Process - to use a mathematical expression that appears in some assessment manuals

Let us suppose that the test has N questions, each of them with n options, the student got right in C of the N questions, and he wandered in E questions. We have then as variables:

N = number of questions, n = number of options of each question, C = number of right questions, E = number of wrong questions, with $0 \leq E \leq N-C$

The extreme 0 of E corresponds to the situation in what the student didn't answer to more questions than those that he got right, and the extreme $N-C$ corresponds to the situation in what the student answered to all the test questions.

In order to compensate the guess factor, some authors defend that we must attribute a proficiency level S given by the following expressions for correcting for guessing:

$$S = C - \frac{E}{n-1} \text{ se } C \geq \frac{N}{n}$$

$$S = 0 \text{ se } C < \frac{N}{n}$$

The underlying principle is that a student, answering a test of N questions with n options, has the "whole chance" of guessing the answers in $C = N/n$ of those questions. If the student got right in those N/n questions, wandering in the remaining $E = N - N/n$ questions, she/he did not go besides those proportionate by the chance of getting right; then, the proficiency level must be zero: $S = 0$.

If we subtract the number of wrong subjects, $N - N/n$, to the number of right subjects, N/n , we don't obtain zero. Nevertheless, if we divide the number of the wrong ones for a factor, x , in order that the difference became zero, a simple equation shows that the value of x is $n - 1$, in agreement with the given expression.

Exemplifying for a group of 6 questions for an objective, each one with 4 options, if the student gets right in the 6 questions ($C = 6$, $E = 0$), his/her proficiency level will be $S = 6 - 0/3 = 6$ points, the maximum level. If solves only 4 questions, getting right in all of them ($C = 4$, $E = 0$), his/her proficiency level will be $S = 4 - 0/3 = 4$ points. It is not introduced a correction factor. If he/she answers to all the 6 questions getting right in only 3 of them ($C = 3$, $E = 3$), his/her proficiency level will be $S = 3 - 3/3 = 2$ points. In this case the student is already introduced a correction factor of 1 point.

The great critic to this process is that it is based in a principle without legitimacy. The student has not "the whole chance" (probability 100%) of getting right by chance in N/n questions, as one can see with the tables 2 and 3. The correction factor given by the above presented expression is exaggerated, when compared with the student's probability to get right by guessing. Then, for instance, in a group of 10 items with 4 options, if a student got right in half of the items, we have:

- Probability of getting right in five items wandering the other five: 5,8 %
- Discount foreseen by the previous expression: $5/3 \times 1/5 = 1/3 = 33,3$ %

2nd Process - to base the correction factor in the tables of probabilities of getting right by chance

Let us suppose that to assess a given objective, the teacher prepared 4 multiple choice questions, each of them with 5 options. The table 3 show us that the probability of getting right at random: in 2 questions is 15,4 %; in 3 questions is 2,6 %; in all the 4 questions is 0,2 %. As the purpose of the group of questions is to assess the proficiency level of a fixed objective, it is important to have in account what

kind of objective it is. First, we go to consider that it is an objective of restricted extent, concerning a quite structured situation, so that the universe of answers is limited and totally attainable by all students. Some authors designate it an *objective at the minimum-essential level*. In this objective, students must reveal a high level of performance, for instance a prerequisite of future learning. In this case, it will be of demanding a quite high attainment level by all students, to admit that the objective was reached. Having in account the student's relatively high probability to have 2 correct answers by chance, in 4 assessment questions to the same objective, the teacher can demand 3 right answers, as minimum proficiency level, since the probability of having 3 right answers by chance is only 2,6%. And, needing to attribute a score (many times these objectives are just qualitatively appraised, as it is only important to know whether the objective was reached or not), the teacher would give the score attributed to the objective to the students that had answered correctly to four or three questions, and zero to the others, considering that two or less correct answers do not guarantee that the students reached the objective; they might have tried to guess total or partially the correct answers.

Another different case is when the objective is of broad extent, it concerns a situation very little structured, where the universe of «good» answers, that prove that the objective was totally reached, is limitless and indefinite. Some authors call it a *development objective*. In this case, it is natural to wait the most varied attainments of the students, depending on the cognitive state in the course for reaching that objective. Now the teacher can vary the difficulty of the questions used to assess the same objective, to discover how far the students get to arrive. If the teacher has to classify the students quantitatively, he/she can give the maximum score to the students who got right in four items, and to give scores as minors as more items have been failed.

In both cases, any correction factor, similarly to what happens to the correction based on the formula, take for granted some presuppositions that may not be verified in many cases: that the tested student chose the options "blindly", that is, all of the answers have the same probability; that all the incorrect answers resulted from a choice based exclusively on luck and not on a lapse, or on a reading mistake, for instance, or even based on an ambiguity of the question statement, as unhappily happens more times than it would be desirable.

On the other hand, these corrections always end for putting the tested students in unequal conditions in what respects to the guessing "technique" and its absence. From students that first eliminate less plausible options and, only then, try the guessing, to the honest students that don't try to guess, there are all the possible situations. We must have in account

that the need to put several items for each objective implies that the number of assessed objectives never will be very big, unless the students have a long time to accomplish the test, what rarely happens. The results of a criterion-referenced test will have a very weak content validity if it is elaborated to assess a great matter extension, with lots of objectives, as, in general, it happens in the exams. In this case, which we intend to gain with the precision of the correction factor, not justified in many cases, we lost in what concern to reach one of the most important technical characteristics that the test results should have: reliability, necessary condition to fidelity.

If we construct a speed test, with many questions for each objective, and we intend to verify the proficiency level, based on more or less correct answers, it can happen that many students, not having any correction factor by random answers, bet seriously in the luck.

In this case, a good student, that honestly only answer the questions that is prepared to answer, can arrive at the end of the time with many less answered questions than the bad students that tried to guess. In this case, a serious reliability problem can appear and the factor correction can be justified. As it is known, we should try to increase as much as possible the reliability of the test results, because this characteristic is a necessary condition, but not enough, of validity. But, it was already shown that the reliability of a test only increases with the introduction of the correction factor for answers by guess, if a positive correlation coefficient exists between the number of omitted answers and the obtained scores (Ebel, 1979). This only happens when the tests are really very extensive, and, consequently, students with better scores are those that leave more questions without answering them, because the worst students answer many questions at random. A test of this nature should be calibrated so that the best students (that the teacher already knows) can answer practically to all, or almost all items. The worst students could answer at random to many questions, but the theory of probabilities will be implacable for them.

4. Conclusions

Concerning to *criterion-referenced tests* we saw that the correction factor, although does not have a very solid base, can be introduced if we adopt some criteria based on tables of probabilities. It will function as a way of demobilizing the students' tendency for answering at random in the questions whose correct answers they are unable to reach.

The less arbitrary criterion is based on the dichotomy *he/she reached – she/he didn't reach* the objective. It should be applied to the *objectives at the minimum-essential level*.

The correct questions by chance could affect the value claims that we want to make about the student cognitive state in what refers to the assessed objectives. But if we have a sufficiently big number of questions for each objective and, besides, the questions have 5 or more options, the introduction of any correction factor in the obtained score becomes perfectly unjustified, since the students have enough time for thinking about the questions and answer honestly to all of them.

If we build a test with a minimum of 12 multiple choice questions with 4 options or with a minimum of 10 questions with 5 options, it becomes perfectly unjustified any correction factor.

As a matter of fact, the table 2 shows that, when we have 12 questions with 4 options, the probability of getting right in half (and to have half of the maximum score) by total chance is only 4 %.

On the other hand, the table 3 shows that, when we have 10 questions with 5 options, the probability of getting right in half (and to have half of the maximum score) by total chance is only 2,6 %.

When we construct a multiple choice test, or a test including two subtests, one of them with multiple choice items, and another with other kind of items, we must have in account these tables of probabilities and the need to use a sufficiently big number of questions, giving time enough to all of the well prepared students can answer to all (or almost all) questions, to avoid the referred reliability problem. And, obviously, it is demanded that all the questions have the largest possible technical quality. Concerning to multiple choice questions, the technical quality demands that (Valadares and Graça, 1998, p. 82): the stem must presents a clearly defined problem (clarity doesn't mean simplicity or triviality); the stem must presents as much information as possible, so that the options can be as short as possible, but, at the same time, only the material needed to make the problem clear and specific; the options must be as homogeneous as possible in what concerns to the content, the form and the extension; the options must be written in a way grammatically coherent with the stem, and disposed in a natural order, if this exist; the options "None of these" or "None of the above" must be used only when the keyed answer can be classified unequivocally as correct or incorrect; the "distracters" should be plausible and attractive, no manifestly wrong for the students; the questions must use novel material and the problems must assess understanding or ability to apply principles or theories; the questions must use the negative only sparingly; the questions must have one, and only one, correct or clearly best answer.

Using an enough number of well formulated multiple choice questions (having in account the presented tables of probabilities), in the great majority of the cases we can abdicate of any correction factor. Using

subtests to the same objectives, we can make studies of reliability through item analyses (Thorndike, 1997, pp. 476-482).

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